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The RSV transcriptome.

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Respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) is a major contributor to infant mortality in the developed world, indicating obvious unmet clinical need despite advanced scientific capabilities. We measured total transcription in cells infected with whole virus in a cell culture model of RSV to study respiratory syncytial virus at the systems level. Cells activated a suite of genes aimed at antiviral defense including genes of the interferon signaling pathway marked by MX2. KMO metabolite induction was a transcriptional signature of RSV infection in human cells, as was alterations in antigen presentation including Erap2 induction. RSV infection resulted in silencing of hnRNPA0. Cellular composition changes included loss of GUCY1A2/GUCY1B3 expression. Nuclease enzymatic cellular perturbations were evident including silencing of Dis3L. RSV silenced ATG4C demonstrating respiratory syncytial virus of autophagy. Nuclear changes included silencing of Setd6 following infection with RSV. We established here programmatic understanding of RSV infection in human cells.

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